

ART STUDIES

THE PSYCHOTECHNIQUE OF THE OPERA SINGER

Odazhiev P.

Associate Professor, Ph.D.

Paisii Hilendarski University of Plovdiv

Abstract

The article examines the specific aspects of the psycho-technique of opera singer-actors. It is pointed out that mastering the professional habits of stage creativity is necessary for the work of the opera performer to be easier and more complete due to the large number of components that should be under control simultaneously. Following all the lines of the role during performance can become a more natural process if the corresponding reflexes are acquired and consciously strengthened over a long period. Creating specialized psychophysical training is justified, and principles and goals are indicated.

Keywords: opera, acting, singer, psycho-technique, theatre, drama, director.

The opera in the 21st century has been greatly influenced by contemporary mass culture, especially in the area of the stage director's *interpretation*. Suppose we leave aside specific aspects and issues related to personal taste and turn to the elements of meaning and esthetics; in that case, we will quickly notice an obvious striving to escape as far as possible from *opera canon*. "Canon" in opera is at times mistakenly (evidently under the sway of emotion) perceived as something archaic, as a cliché (referring to the physical discrepancy between the performers and the characters they represent, to "dusty," sham, unnatural mannerisms, etc.) instead of as a system of inherent rules and norms that serve to stabilize the basic structural correlations between the art of music and the art of drama. Artificiality, understood as a *profanation* of opera performance, has hardly anything to do with the sort of (essentially ideal) artificiality that is the *fundamental canonic principle* of opera art, a principle that determined this art's unique power of emotional and esthetic impact upon the audience.

The possibility of interpretation of the opera canon by modern stage directing is directly related to familiarity with and recognition of the principles that determine the psycho-physical situation of the singer-actors - a situation that is proper and uniquely to their art and differs from the art of the dramatic actor. The question arises as to how to reconcile the attitude of dramatic stage direction, which primarily stresses visualization, with the predominance of music, which defines opera. The classical foundation of opera esthetics leads to very distinct ways of forming vocal-scenic skills, which is in complete contradiction with the traditional psychological notions about the presence of the dramatic actor on stage. The view that the two are the same and the mechanical understanding of the analogy between the nature of acting skills in opera and drama lead to dis-coordination between expressive devices and put the opera performer in an ambiguous situation so that he/she is forced to perform tasks not proper to him/her,

and that contradict the nature of his/her work. The aspects related to the performing skills of the opera singer, particularly the singer's training, are not linked only to *coordination between musical and acting habits*, as is assumed in modern opera pedagogy¹, though this is a very complicated problem. In selecting the kind of *actor's habits* (included in the coordination system) that might determine on-stage behavior in harmony with classicist esthetics, it is precisely the latter that becomes a stable element of the canon of opera art. This is a question of applied acting skills, typical of the genre, and pointedly aimed at specific means of expression rather than a question of fundamental acting skills.

The excessive dramatization and psychological emphasis, which is a deviation from the classical esthetic norms of opera performance, is a result of Stanislavsky's influence (in Russia and other countries) on the art of opera. The patterns, fake emotions, and declamation in theatrical art, but also in opera that characterized the Italian and French companies touring Russia at that time, who were far below the high standards set by Coquelin and Diderot, motivated Stanislavsky to work in permanent opposition to this kind of acting and to create his own "system," which appealed to the emotional nature of the actor and applied to the style of 19th and 20th-century realist drama but is in contradiction with the style and principles of high tragedy and classicist drama, for which "presentation," and not "experiencing," was fundamental, and not a question of esthetic choice. Stanislavsky admired the voices of the talented Italian opera singers on tour in Russia. Yet, he rejected their on-stage helplessness, the "conventionality" of their stage behavior, and outward impressiveness, which he called "Italianshtina" ("Italian style" in the pejorative sense). Later on, he would assert that most of the patterns and stage absurdities in opera originated precisely under the influence of the Italians. Fighting against these clichés became his life's work.

What is the dividing line between the necessary scenic conventionality and the fake, imitation theatrical conventionality? These questions excited Stanislavsky

¹ Вж. Стародубцев, В.В. Методика обучения мастерству актера и режиссуре оперы. Автореферат; М., ГИТИС, 2011;

http://www.gitis.net/rus/postgraduate/notices/s/starodubtsev_auto.shtml [Starodubtsev, V. V. Methodics of Training in Acting and Opera Direction (in Russian)]

at the times when he suffered failures in the genre of tragedy. His work and creative efforts in the Opera Study, as presented in Kristi's book *Stanislavsky in Opera Theatre*, clearly indicate that in acknowledging certain qualities of the opera score that distinguish it from a dramatic text in dramatic theatre, he did not offer the singers-actors any different methods by which to master their roles, distinct from those practiced in dramatic theatre. Stanislavsky translated his "system" without any particular changes and entered into numerous contradictions with the vocal performers, which ultimately failed to produce the expected enthusiasm on the part of the young trainees. In any case, the emphasis on the dramatic was shifted, putting a long-lasting mark on the opera singer in Russia.

The view that the "dramatic element" (the actor's playing) is secondary to the "musical" element (vocal performance) is a particular problem, a reflection of the two-component structure of opera in general. It expresses the disparity between the two arts that form opera – music and drama, in the interaction of which the musical component is dominant. The construction of opera performance that has been left as a legacy of the 400 years of opera history includes the whole polyphony of esthetical and theatrical ideas, conceptual models, and particular practices. The main difference, however, runs along the dividing line between the dominance of the "musical" and the "dramatic"; hence, it is the area of prevalence of the concrete (the psychological) and the metaphoric (the abstract). I should make the provision that the present article has no intention of clarifying the key positions and concepts of the work of the opera singer-actor or deducing the strict regularities needed for the training and realization of this type of creative work; this book can only outline the possible directions and principles of synthesis. The world practice of opera pedagogy does not yet have adequate solutions that would allow the formation of a consistent training system for opera performers which fully reflects the specificity of opera. Can only give examples of mechanical translation of theatrical techniques and practices or training in the course of practice, based on observations and surmises.

As practice has shown, the opera performer can function (more or less successfully) even without having skills in acting, and world opera is full of such examples. This is because the primary means of expression of the singer-actors is their voice, vocal capacity, and technique. At the same time, dramatic acting qualities have a complementary, but not decisive, importance for the quality of their art. Asked in an interview whether he finds it more challenging to work with singer-actors or dramatic actors, Peter Brook answered, "The singer-actor differs from the dramatic actor in that he is a master of his craft. Behind him lie hard years of

study and stubborn work. He has learned music, correct breathing, and vocal technique. He has studied languages. This gives him a firm ground. He has mastered a craft that will always hold him. That is why the singer-actor with intuition, stamina, and willingness to be truthful can be more true to life and natural than the dramatic actor. He does not need to do anything special. At times he may even remain himself."²

The problem mentioned above, viewed in the context of stage directing, clearly points to a priority: all elements and practices used by the stage director to manifest the dramatic content of the spectacle through the performance of the actor-singers must gravitate around their *voice*, which is the basis, the "spring" of sensual-emotional structure, while their physical expressiveness must be a complementary element that is in harmony with the "artificiality" of the phenomenon of voice-instrument. Of decisive importance here is the understanding of the typological *difference* between the art of the opera actor and that of the dramatic actor, a difference closely related to the *object* of the two arts.

In dramatic art, the object of the actor's art is *action*, which may be compared to the *musical-vocal line* in the case of the singer. In dramatic theatre, action is self-initiated by the actor on stage, unfolds according to specific rules, and has a complex structure – physical, textual, inner voice, and imagination. It follows a complex, nuanced logic of conduct that must be deciphered according to the author's text and unfolds in multi-layered psycho-physical action on stage. What leads the action is the fixed text, which is subject to *interpretation*, while the goal is to create a character (a dramatic character). In opera, a character is also created, but through the unfolding of the vocal line of the role, which is fixed above all by musical means and represents an excellent structure: rhythm, dynamics, heights of sound cannot be changed arbitrarily by the performer, the degree of improvisation in the auditory space is reduced to a minimum. While dramatic actors attain high emotional states by uplifting their souls (their psyche) – as in the catastrophic experience of King Lear in the wilderness, Medea killing her children, etc. – in opera, the *vocal score* leads the actor and already contains emotional intensity. Having in mind this fully fixed and given structure, Y. V. Bogatyrev has very aptly compared the vocal line of the opera singer to the "pure structure of the Ancient Greek mask"³, which points to the description of the mask made by Y. Barboy, as something "immovably determined, fully manifest and given beforehand – it is a pure structure, shorn of history and, thereby, having achieved full determination, an object massively equal to itself."⁴ The emphasis here justly falls on the mask as an independent phenomenon not liable to destruction, breaking

² Брук, П. Блуждающая точка: Статьи. Выступления. Интервью. Изд. СПб., М., Артист. Режиссер. Театр. 1996; Гл. VII Сороколетняя война. „Кармен”, Интервью с Филиппом Альбера после премьеры спектакля „Трагедия Кармен” в Буфф-дю-Нор в ноябре 1981; с.97-98. [Brooke. P. The Shifting Point (in Russian)]

³ Виж: Богатырев В.Ю. Структура партии-роли. Вестник Челябинского государственного университета.

Филология. Искусствоведение. Челябинск, 2009, № 10 (148), с.164-168. [Bogatyrev, V. Y. The Structure of Roles (in Russian)]

⁴ Барбой, Ю.М. Структура действия и современный спектакль. Л., 1988, с.63. [Barboy, Y. M. The Structure of Action and Modern Spectacle (in Russian)]

down into parts. "Such a definition of the mask in Ancient Greek theater," Barboy points out, "probably corresponds precisely to the quality of the vocal score in opera. Its tone and rhythm are strictly harmoniously developed and is a perfect structure, despotically predefined for performance by the composer".⁵

A stage character is created in both arts, and both arts deal with human behavior. Still, in opera, this behavior is displayed through the conventionally encoded language of vocalization, or emotions are mediated through *additional technical skills*. That is why the talent of the singer-actors is defined foremost by their vocal capacity, and the artist's vocal technique is crucial. Dramatic art is the only art that does not require any training in addition to natural talent: singers sing, musicians play instruments, and painters paint. The instrument of the opera artist is his soul, expressed through body and behavior. That is why this art may be the easiest (not requiring special skills) or the most difficult (for the same reason). The play of the soul is a subtle and hard-to-pinpoint process: it cannot be measured through the objective criteria of vocal art, ballet, etc. The means of expression are locked in the actor's organism, in their psychophysique. As for "truth" and "falsehood," the "organic" or the "technical," it is challenging to establish rules and criteria here; the truth is always a relative and flexible concept, so the boundary separating the professional from the amateur is hard to draw here. The avant-garde Russian director and pedagogue A. Vasiliev states, "Theater is a vulgar art. It is not like painting or music, where there are strict correspondences. It's hard to know who is playing what in Theater."⁶

Striving to devise the professional foundations of the art of theatre, it is not coincidental that Stanislavsky turned to music and ballet as arts with stable and well-established professional parameters. Meyerhold did the same when he marked down his stagings on a note scale to create a general theatrical "score writing"; we know that his attempt was unsuccessful.

That is why the need to create an *actor's psychotechnique* arose precisely in the 20th century, a technique that would serve as a lever for stabilizing, controlling, and guiding all the inner processes in the actor. Before that, acting was imitative – it followed specific models. It developed according to a given actor's abilities and skills to assimilate the model he was following. Assimilating the "psychotechnique" invented by Stanislavsky was equal in complexity and difficulty to vocal technique and took years to learn. The partial, superficial lessons in acting that an opera performer is given during their training create in, on the one hand, a misconception as to the complexity of the actor's profession (i.e., they perceive it as something easy that anyone can learn). On the other hand, these

lessons do not provide the set of tools that a future performer will need for their artistic presence in performing an opera role.

At the same time, it is not true that training in acting is not necessary for the opera singer. Besides being a musical art, opera is a *stage art*. Music plays the dominant role in the combination of musical and dramatic, but it "dominates" in the context of the stage; there is no way to eliminate the stress factor of being "on stage" for the opera performer or the whole set of fundamental actor's habits that teach the body of the actor to deal with the psychophysiological changes that occur as a result of being before the public. Stage anxiety is one of the crucial problems of the opera performer. At times, the severity of the problem stays with actors and singing actors throughout their careers, despite their experience in performing on stage. "Many historical facts indicate that even the most experienced musician and actor is not insured against a flop on stage if he is not prepared for the performance. The basic signs of stage anxiety syndrome are related to trembling of the hands, lips, and knees, failure of the voice or hearing, and the inability to focus on the performance of the work. When this state acquires unnecessarily painful forms, it is unpleasant for the performer and linked to professional losses."⁷

In my personal experience as a teacher in acting and singer-actor, I have had occasions to observe in students and colleagues examples of increased anxiety and extreme neuroticism before going on stage at competitions, castings, or rehearsals. On stage, "blocks" can "paralyze" the performer, and though they may be genuinely talented in vocal skills, they cannot show this as they cannot cope with stage stress.

In this connection, there is undoubtedly a need for special training to acquire psychological stability, adapt to the stage, and train the singer-actor to work in the unnatural conditions of being on stage; this training must precede the first earnest performances on stage. The main obstacle, stage anxiety, hampers the capacity of *concentration*, which leads to *muscular tension*. The deep immersion within the performance creates a circle of attention that Stanislavsky calls "the little circle of attention," recommending it to the actors inclined to be very anxious on stage.⁸ But the "little circle of attention," as effective as it might be, does not always work due to muscle blockages. If excessive muscular tension arises, it is not possible to concentrate even in the "small circle." Special exercises are needed to relax the muscles, which should become automatic during on-stage performance. We also know that muscle tension disturbs the natural, coordinated activity of all the systems providing creative activity.

The performance of an opera singer requires preparation not only in mastering the vocal score but also in forming a *stable creative self-confidence on stage*,

⁵ Богатырев, В.Ю. Структура партии-роли, с.164. [Bogatuyev (ibid) (in Russian)]

⁶ Богданова, П. Уроки Анатолия Васильева. Современная драматургия. 2006, Ном. 3, с.192-202. [Bogdanova. P. The Lessons of Anatoliy Vasiliev (in Russian)]

⁷ Голубева, Е. Проблема сценического волнения. Ростовская государственная консерватория (академия) им. С.В.Рахманинова; Ростов-на-Дону, с.1. <http://www.rae.ru/forum2012/pdf/0297.pdf>

⁸ Станиславский, К.С. Собр. соч. в 8 т. М., Государственное издательство „Искусство“, 1957 [Educating the Actor (in Russian)]

which implies the natural functioning of the body in case a stage “breakdown” occurs. That makes it possible, according to Stanislavsky, “for every feeling created inside to be reflected outside.” Later on, Jerzy Grotowski would seek the same psychological “state,” the kind of transformation of the actor, where “the barrier vanishes between thought and feel, soul and body, conscious and subconscious, views and instincts, sex and brain; if the actor succeeds in doing this, he has achieved plenitude.”⁹

The contradiction between the actor’s play and his vocal performance is part of the overall contradictory unity of the art of opera, which includes within itself heterogeneous principles. This contradiction often leads to an underestimation of the artistic component of the professional skill of the opera singer, particularly the freedom of on-stage presence that permits a free flow of interconnected processes between the musical and the dramatic. This freedom is the *preliminary condition* for creativity. The well-known Russian specialist in the psychology of opera performance, Ivetta Gersamiya, writes, “The principle of performance is determined by the certain state of preparedness, by the force of which psychophysical powers are mobilized and actualized, the powers needed to create a given vocal-scenic character.”¹⁰

In many musical academies worldwide, the achievements of modern applied psychology are already being used, those related to the methods of *psychological self-regulation*, by which students can train their organism (which is their creative tool) to work naturally under the unnatural conditions of the stage. For instance, in his article “Psychological self-regulation in the process of actor’s training,” Andrey Alekseyev describes the training results, based on the methods of psychological self-regulation, of students in GITIS in Moscow in 1976 – 1978. The experimental work aimed to establish whether psychological self-regulation would help enhance the creative potential of students studying to be actors. Psychological self-regulation (PSR) is based on the theory of Academician P. K. Anokhin on functional systems. According to Alekseyev, one of the essential applications of the theory can be illustrated by the following example: when a person takes part in some activity, changes in the body are determined by that activity. In shifting from walking to running, the leg muscles begin to work more actively, the heart beats faster, breathing becomes more profound, and several other changes occur in the body linked to the new dynamic nature of the movement. The more prepared a person is, the easier and smoother this transition becomes, and vice versa. The coordinated, harmonious work of different organs lies at the basis of this shift. Alekseyev writes, “If we turn to the actor’s profession, an example of uncoordinated work of the

separate organs and systems is the condition before going on stage when some muscle’ blockages’ occur because of the intense excitement of the nervous system. As a result, the actor stops controlling himself, his movements become rigid and uncoordinated, and his speech is distorted somehow.”¹¹

On the other hand, in the psychology of acting skills field, some studies have shown that stress-provoking factors may stimulate creativity. Thus, in the book *The Actor and His Alter Ego* by I. Silantieva and Y. Klimenkov, interviewed professional actors point out that stage stress has the helpful effect of provoking self-confidence: “This is a kind of stress to which I gladly abandon myself”; “The impact is beneficial. There comes a feeling of relief, renewal, physical energy appears”; “If you feel bad, after the performance an uplift occurs, the painful feelings disappear”; “It is a flight!. Your forces are restored. If the ‘watergates’ are opened, the wasted energy comes back. The harmony is preserved.”¹² Acting experience has also shown that “stress-provoking factors may also serve as a sort of key giving access to the subconscious level of the psyche, and that is where lies inspiration, “illumination,” “find,” where memories are provoked, associative thinking.”¹³ At times, under certain conditions – for instance, in case of extreme on-stage exhaustion – a “shock of conscience” occurs, and the mental hypertension suddenly releases the subconscious. At times, Stanislavsky tired out the actors utterly (according to the memories of actress S. Pilyavskaya). Seeking to produce a state of “freedom,” he would repeat hundreds of times, “I don’t believe it!” and “Take it from the start!”, until finally somebody would burst into tears or fall to the floor from exhaustion... But, as a rule, “the second breathing” would open up after that, and the rehearsal produced the sought result.¹⁴ Of course, modern stage pedagogy has many exercises that are less burdensome and aim to reduce the tension of the performer *beforehand, by suitable training*, and open the way to the subconscious for him.

The opera singer needs a special psycho technique, just as the dramatic actor does. The salient questions are about the *specific* nature of this technique, how it can combine the management of vocal and acting mechanisms in a unified regulated process, and what the mutual subordination of these processes should be. Psychotechnique (from the Greek word *techne*—art, mastery) is a branch of psychology that deals with applying psychological knowledge to solve practical problems. The German psychologists William Stern and Hugo Munsterberg conducted the first research in this field.

As mentioned above, Stanislavsky introduced the concept of “actor’s psycho-technique” when he began to design his *System*. His work was strongly influenced

⁹ Grotowski, J. *Towards a Poor Theatre*. Methuen. Drama. London, 1975, p.44.

¹⁰ Герсамя И.Е. К проблеме психологии творчества певца. Тбилиси: Мецниереба, 1985.; с. 20

¹¹ Алексеев А.В. Сб. Диагностика и развитие актерской одаренности. Ленинград, Мин. культ. РСФСР, ЛГИТМИК, 1986. [Gersamiy, I. E. On the Problem of the psychology of the Singer’s Work (in Russian)]

¹² Вж.: Силантьева, И.И., Ю.Г.Клименко. Актер и его alter ego. Научно-художественное издание. М., Грааль. ВИНТИ, 2000, с.441. [Silantieva, I. I. and Y. G. Llimenko. *The Actor and His Alter ego* (in Russian)]

¹³ Пак там, с.432. [Ibid (in Russian)]

¹⁴ Пак там, с.432. [Ibid (in Russian)]

by psychotechnique in Yoga and by the studies of the French psychologist and psychopathologist Théodule Ribot (especially his discoveries on the mechanisms of memory, emotions, and conscious attention), and later on, by the discoveries of I. P. Pavlov and I. M. Sechenov. Actor's psycho-technique today means a system of means and instruments for solving professional acting problems; the term is often used to train actors. However, its meaning is at times incorrectly understood, and hence psycho technique in general, and its components that the perfection of the practice directly depends on, are rarely underestimated. Psychotechnique is the *neural and physical organization of the actor*, which influences their ability to assimilate, assess, and carry out a specific creative task. It is the skill to operate with processes like thinking, attention, imagination, emotion, movement, and speech. The psycho-technique's quality and level of perfection are determined by how quickly and precisely the actor can fulfill a given task. The main aim is to shape precise reflexes to help the organism work correctly to achieve the set tasks. Psychotechnique aims to establish *automatism and stability* so that the mind will use less effort and energy and shift to the fulfillment of the more problematic tasks and essential places in the work of the organism, which requires *maximal energy*.

Modern Russian music studies, for which an increasingly frequent and detailed focus on the methodology of opera art has become typical, actively use the concept of "psycho-technique of the opera singer." In studies by Prof. V. I. Yushmanov, the idea is limited to psychological awareness, control, and management of *vocal processes*. For V. Starodubtsev and V. Bogatyrev, it concerns the conscious management of the actor's play, and these authors study several elements of its specificity. These focus differences are again related to the problems of musical and dramatic synthesis. The apparent need for combining the two psychotechniques – that of the vocal element and that of on-stage performance – to form a *new, mixed type of psychotechnique* is, however, a very complex problem, mainly because, traditionally, training in vocal and acting skills is not done simultaneously, and because of the existing differences between the nature of music and drama, which hamper the application of a unified approach.

To summarize, it is possible to outline at least two trends - an attempt has been made to discover a common algorithm in the combination of singing and artistic technique (in this case, based on conscious energy modeling; of course, it should be noted that the degree of elaboration of the two processes, vocal and acting, is far from equal). Also, the understanding is disregarded, according to which the "dramatic component" is limited only to the plot framework of the opera; it is seen as integrated with the *irrationality* of the music.

Regarding questions about the specific features of acting training for opera performers as the most problematic aspect of their professional growth and as a condition of productive interaction with the opera di-

rector, we should point out that this training cannot generally be separated from the *esthetic requirements* of opera as a genre. In addition to stable psychotechnique (which adapts the singer-actor to the stage and involves the *basic*, and one could say technical, qualities of muscular relaxation and controlled attention), it is necessary to revisit, *in relation to the genre*, the other elements of actor's psychotechnique (if we follow Stanislavsky's method), i.e., imagination, emotions, action, movement, which are *structural* to the performance. Most important here is the essential idea that it is necessary to preserve the *irrational element of acting* as something that harmonizes with the irrationality of music, which in its spirit and the practical aim is the opposite of the rational, analytical idea contained in psychological acting style.

References

1. Алексеев, А.В. Психическая саморегуляция в процессе обучения мастерству актера. В Сб. Диагностика и развитие актерской одаренности. Ленинград. Мин. культуры РСФСР; ЛГИТМИК. 1986
2. Барбой, Ю.М. Структура действия и современный спектакль. Л., 1988
3. Богатырев, В.Ю. Структура партии-роли // Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. Филология. Искусствоведение. – Челябинск, 2009, № 10 (148), с.164-168
4. Брук, П. Блуждающая точка: Статьи. Выступления. Интервью. М., Изд. СПб. Артист. Режиссер. Театр. 1996
5. Васильев, А. Дневник (парижского) режиссера // Искусство кино, 1995, № 18, с.94
6. Герсамя, И.Е. К проблеме психологии творчества певца. Тбилиси, Мецниереба, 1985
7. Стародубцев, В.В. Методика обучения мастерству актера и режиссуре оперы. Автореферат. М., ГИТИС, 2011
8. Богданова, П. Уроки Анатолия Васильева. Современная драматургия. 2006, Ном. 3, с.192-202
9. Е. Голубева, Проблема сценического волнения. Ростовская государственная консерватория им. С.В. Рахманинова; Ростов-на-Дону, с.1. <http://www.rae.ru/forum2012/pdf/0297.pdf>
10. Станиславский, К.С. Собр. соч. в 8 т. М., Государственное издательство „Искусство”, 1957
11. Силантьева, И.И., Ю.Г. Клименко. Актер и его alter ego. Научно-художественное издание. Грала. М., ВИНТИ, 2000
12. Barba E. The Paper Canoe. A Guide to Theatre Anthropology. Routledge. London and New York. 1995
13. Grotowski Jerzy. Towards a Poor Theatre. Methuen. Drama. London. 1975
14. David, F. Ostwald. Acting for Singers, Oxford University Press, 2005
15. LizBeth Abeyta Lucca. Acting Techniques for Opera. Vivace Opera, 2007
16. Mark Ross Clark. Singing, Acting and Movement in Opera. A Guide to Singer getics. Indiana University Press. Bloomington&Indianapolis, 2002